

Video Shot Discovery through Text2Video Embeddings in a News Analytics Dashboard

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Abstract—This demonstration will show how video shot discovery through joint text-video embedding has been integrated into a journalistic workflow through a news monitoring dashboard with the purpose of identifying suitable video material for the creation of immersive scenes around a chosen news story or topic.

Keywords— video segmentation, video embedding, multimodal search, Generative AI, video to 3D models

I. INTRODUCTION

Journalists and newsrooms make use of dedicated software tools to monitor online conversation and news reporting (social media, global news sources), for various purposes: identify breaking news stories, understand how stories or topics are being reported in different places by different sources, or find relevant content about a story to use in their own reporting. In the EU-funded TRANSMIXR project¹, our news partners (led by Agence France-Presse or AFP) use the webLyzard Web intelligence dashboard² for news monitoring and content discovery. An usual search result in the dashboard’s Web UI (of news articles matching a search for “fire”) is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Initial search results screen of the dashboard

One of the use cases, which has also been explored by the authors in previous projects [1][2], is that of finding video content relevant to a selected news topic or story. Besides the collection of online textual content (Web pages or social media posts) via Web crawling or social network APIs respectively, the webLyzard dashboard was extended to collect video content (YouTube or broadcasters’ video archives, as long as an API would be available). The binary video file is not stored on our servers – rather the content is

analysed and the metadata is stored in a highly scalable, multi-sharded Elastic index. To begin with, we had text-based metadata extracted from the video metadata available from its source (e.g. from YouTube the video title and description) and a text-based search over the collected videos in the dashboard. However, this is limiting as video material can only be found if words in the search query match words in the video metadata such as its title and description. It does not help a user who is looking for video of a specific object, situation or event. This is a typical search requirement of a journalist or newsroom who wants to re-use video material (with permission, but it could also be within their own archives) for a new production – e.g. in making a report about a recent fire in a city, they may want video of the buildings before the damage occurred. Typically, such video will form a smaller part of the whole video content returned by the textual search and the user still needs to extract only those parts which match their visual requirement (showing the buildings).

We therefore extended our video metadata, indexed by webLyzard technology, with the results of video analysis over the actual visual features in the video. Video segmentation provided time stamps for individual shots and scenes in the video. Concept detection was then applied to each shot/scene in the video, which is a form of multi-label classification where for each shot/scene the probability of it showing each concept from a predefined set of concepts is calculated and those concepts whose probability is higher than a set threshold are annotated to that shot/scene. The dashboard was extended so that, for a set of search results that are all video contents and those contents had been analyzed by the above process, results could be filtered by one or more concepts. While this made it possible for a user to ‘drill down’ to a video shot or scene that showed something specific that they are looking for (e.g. from a longer news report, the journalist may only want to see shots of the *fire (concept)* engulfing the building), it was highly dependent on the set of concepts the concept detection model had been trained for (e.g. if “fire” were one of those concepts or not). In such a model, there could only ever be a fixed set of finite concept types for which it has been trained (just as in classification models), so that a search for shots of “flames” would return zero results (as flames is not a concept the classifier is trained for) despite its close semantic meaning to “fire”.

In this demo, we will show our latest solution for text-based search over video shots in the webLyzard dashboard. The user is free to formulate a natural language text query over

¹ <https://www.transmixr.eu>

² <https://www.webyzard.com>

the video collections (we have YouTube and AFP videos). The text is matched to the video shots whose visual content is closest in *semantic meaning*, e.g. a “flames” search should not be too different from a search for “fire”. As a result, we overcome the previous limitations of the concept detection approach.

II. THE TEXT2VIDEO IMPLEMENTATION

To make video assets available to search and retrieval systems, it is first necessary to analyse the video and output a machine-processable description of the video's structure and semantics (descriptive metadata). A video analysis service developed in the TRANSMIXR project is accessed through a REST API and can be initiated by issuing a POST call, and the request JSON must include the video URL. The analysis of a submitted video is done in three main phases. First, the submitted video URL is downloaded and temporarily stored on the server. Then, the video is temporally segmented into scenes and shots, and finally, a feature extraction module analyses the video segments and extracts semantic features using cross-modal networks.

The video analysis service supports videos from the most popular video platforms, such as YouTube, Facebook and Twitter/X, as well as videos hosted on file hosting platforms. The analysis of the videos starts on a temporal fragmentation level, and a video is first decomposed into scenes and shots. Scenes are temporally and semantically video segments that represent a story-telling part of a video. On the other hand, shots are segments, which are a continuous capture by a single camera. A scene is typically a larger temporal fragment of a video and consists of one or more shots. We utilize the TransNet network [3] to temporally segment the video into scenes and shots. TransNet is a deep-learning architecture designed to detect shot boundaries in videos. Shot boundary detection involves identifying transitions between shots in a video sequence, such as cuts, fades, wipes, and dissolves. TransNet utilizes a convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture to analyze video frames and detect these transitions automatically. Finally, every video is decomposed into a sequence of video shots, and from every shot, we extract keyframes with a sampling rate of 2fps.

After extracting shots' representative keyframes, the Text2Video module is utilized to extract the cross-modal visual semantic embeddings. The goal of the Text2Video module is to extract semantic information from both textual and visual data in the form of embeddings (multidimensional vectors) and to link text with video shots by representing those semantics in the same vector space and enabling the free-text video search. For this, we follow a two-fold strategy. First, we utilize the TxV [4] network, a cross-modal network consisting of two key sub-networks designed for text-based video search. Secondly, inspired by the best-performing approach [16] and based on the conclusions of the TRECVID Ad-hoc video search 2023 [10], where the utilization of multiple cross-modal networks leads to improved performance, we also utilize numerous pre-trained cross-modal text-image networks as video-frame feature extractors. Apart from various pre-trained models of the vanilla CLIP [5] model, we also utilize pre-trained models from SLIP [6], BLIP [7], BLIP-2 [8], and LaCLIP [9].

TxV can capture complex semantic relationships between words and visual features, leading to more comprehensive and accurate representations of multimodal data. This network is

designed to combine textual and visual features to develop multiple cross-modal common latent spaces. The TxV network is trained using a combination of four large-scale video caption datasets MSR-VTT [15], TGIF [13], ActivityNet [12] and VateX [14]. Also, we trained multiple models using three learning rates (10^{-4} , $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$, 10^{-5}) and two optimizers (i.e., Adam and RMSprop), and we combined the results of these models to achieve the best possible performance. A tailored version of the TxV network is utilized in the TRECVID Ad-hoc video search (AVS) 2023 benchmarking task [10][11], where it achieved Mean Extended Inferred Average Precision (MxinfAP) equal to 0.24.

After extracting the frame-level embeddings from the abovementioned text-image models, we develop shot-level embeddings by aggregating the frame embeddings using mean pooling. These generated embeddings are combined with the shot-level embeddings extracted by the TxV model. All of the generated vectors are returned as part of the service response. In order to learn how to combine all these embeddings, we follow a weighting aggregation approach at the query time, where each network is assigned a unique weight value. During the training phase, we performed a grid search over these weights to determine their optimal values and evaluated our method's performance on the TRECVID AVS 2023 evaluation dataset, achieving MxinfAP equal to 0.299.

The analysed video shot collection can now be searched via textual query even though the extracted video shots do not have any associated textual metadata (at best, there is a title and description for the complete video only). When a user makes a textual query over the video shot collection, the Text2Video module encodes the query using the TxV network and all the aforementioned text-image models. Then, it calculates the similarity between these textual embeddings and the corresponding video shot embeddings using cosine similarity as a distance measure between vectors and develops similarity lists (one for each cross-modal network). Then, we utilize the learned optimal weighting values described above to aggregate the similarities between the user's query and all the shots from the video shot collection into a single list, representing the final similarity. Fig. 2 below illustrates the components and workflow for the video analysis and retrieval.

Fig. 2. Video analysis and retrieval system overview

III. VIDEO SHOT DISCOVERY IN THE DASHBOARD

The textual search over video collections has been integrated into the webLyzard dashboard for the TRANSMIXR project. As it includes Agence France-Presse

(AFP) content which cannot be made public, the dashboard is not publicly accessible. After login, data sources with video can be selected which have been analyzed by the Text2Video module to provide video shot embeddings stored in an Elastic index. The text2video search capability is integrated into the Web interface of the dashboard through a newly implemented service we named *embedify*. This service can take as input the text of a search query and determine the set of video shots, which are semantically closest to the meaning of the text. To do this, we also convert the text query into a multidimensional vector embedding using the same approach as the Text2Video module. The video shots within the current search context of the dashboard (the selected data sources, the date and language settings) are sorted by cosine similarity between their embeddings and the text embedding of the search. The closest shots to the search query are returned.

As an example, a journalist explores recent news stories in the dashboard at the end of April, which they can do visually using the *story graph* visualization (Fig. 3)[17]. This shows the distribution of terms in the global news coverage over time, clustered by term co-occurrence into stories, with the relative sizes of each cluster (number of news documents related to that story) highlighting the scale of coverage of each story.

Fig. 3. Story graph visualization of news document clusters in April 2024 highlighting the stories about the solar eclipse.

They identify the topic of the solar eclipse in the global news coverage as an interesting subject for a video report (after all, only people in the line of totality could experience the eclipse on April 8, 2024, but video of the eclipse provides a means for anyone to “re-live” the eclipse afterwards). They want to find relevant video material within the available data sources, having selected the story in the dashboard’s story graph visualization as their search query (in this case the terms “eclipses” and “totality” are used). Our sources are AFP video material (restricted to AFP members) and public YouTube video* (in a real news scenario, the uploader of the video should be contacted for permission for video re-use). In our case, we find 8 YouTube videos and 3 AFP videos. A part of the search results in the dashboard is shown in Fig. 4 (* the YouTube feed is a specially curated data collection from YouTube via its API, not a search over the whole of YouTube). By restricting the date range in the search to 8 April and afterwards, we can focus on video recordings of the actual eclipse, removing videos from before the event. We conclude, in this case, with two AFP and two YouTube videos that are available for immersive content creation.

Fig. 4. Video results from AFP and YouTube sources for solar eclipse

Finding full videos related to the eclipse is not enough, since the journalist is only interested in video contents of the moment of totality (when the moon fully covers the sun’s disk, blocking all direct sunlight). The journalist needs to drill down to the shots where there is clear coverage of the eclipse occurring, ideally not only showing the sky but also the surroundings (at ground level), rather than other content of these videos such as news anchors reporting the eclipse, interviews with eclipse spectators, etc. Here we can make use of the Text2Video module to make the relevant video shots discoverable via textual search queries. Queries such as “sun”, “spectators” and “city” were used to find different shots (of the sun during the eclipse, of people watching the eclipse from the ground wearing protective eyewear, drone shots of the eclipse taking place over urban areas). Fig. 5 shows an advanced search with *embedify* in the dashboard, with a conjunctive query (Boolean AND) being used to select shots of a solar eclipse together with either spectators or a city being visible in the shot (a disjunctive query or Boolean OR).

Fig. 5. Sample *embedify* search in the dashboard for relevant video shots

After a query is made, the matching video shots (those with a similarity to the search query within a certain threshold) are listed in the dashboard with the option to preview them (through a play button, the video shot is played back within the Web interface) and “pin” those selected by the journalist for export (through the pin button, the URL of the video with a media fragment identifier for the specific shot is saved). Other content can also be exported from the dashboard: text from the video metadata (title and description) as well as images (keyframes extracted in the video analysis). These could be used to provide more context around the chosen topic. Fig. 6 shows a sample video shot and image content discoverable within the dashboard.

Fig. 6. Example content from the dashboard. (left) a video shot of the sun from a YouTube video, (right) a keyframe image from an AFP video.

At the end, the journalist has selected one suitable video shot of the solar eclipse in the sky and one suitable video shot of the solar eclipse taking place over a barren landscape in Antarctica. Having pinned both in the dashboard, their URLs are exported so that they can access the video content and potentially use it in their own report (again, in a real world use case, they would request permission to the owner of the YouTube video).

IV. CONCLUSION

Our demonstration will show a sample workflow for video shot discovery through the Text2Video embeddings in a news monitoring dashboard. A user can explore current or past news stories and select a topic or story of interest. They can then check for video content matching that topic or story. Finally, they can access the *embedify* search functionality to make a natural language text query over the videos, receiving a list of semantically similar video shots as a result. If they wanted, they can now export the references to those video shots (e.g. YouTube URL with media fragment identifier) in order to access the video content directly (e.g., to embed it into another piece of content).

This work addresses the need to find visually relevant video (segments) within a larger collection. We analyze the entire video file and apply video segmentation and visual feature analysis. Innovatively, rather than generating an explicit annotation as the result of the content analysis (usually labels or a textual description, stored in a metadata document associated with the video file), we create a neural network-based high-dimensional embedding of each video shot. Through the Text2video module, we match those shot embeddings with a text embedding generated from a search query. This makes individual shots available to a textual search independent of descriptive metadata (which is typically missing from video segments). We showed how this Text2video is integrated into a Web-based dashboard so that journalists can search and browse shots intuitively, on the basis of natural language textual queries.

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Details for on-site demonstration:

All we need is a large monitor and a HDMI connection. The dashboard can be shown via its online Web interface from our laptop. Audio (for the video playback) is welcome but we could use the laptop's speaker as it should not be too loud in any case.